

APP4AD, the Advanced Payload data Processing for Autonomy & Decision agent for future EO and planetary exploration missions

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APP4AD is a project funded by the Italian Space Agency aimed at fostering the development of innovative ideas in on-board space technologies. The main challenge of APP4AD is to enable on-board systems to process data from sensors and scientific instruments, and to perform evaluations that are traditionally handled by human operators. This is achieved through the use of autonomous systems and artificial intelligence. The outcome of APP4AD will be a prototype of on-board software that can be integrated into typical operational missions. Two reference scenarios have been defined for demonstration purposes: one in Earth Observation and the other in planetary exploration. The Earth Observation scenario aims to detect oil spills on-board in a timely manner using SAR data. The planetary exploration scenario aims to enable a rover to explore Mars or any other rocky celestial body almost entirely autonomously. The development team is composed of a consortium of three Italian SMEs: Planetek Italia, Geophysical Applications Processing, and S.A.T.E. Systems & Advanced Technologies Engineering.

1 Introduction

In the realm of space exploration, the constant evolution of technological capabilities necessitates an equally dynamic approach to operational strategies. Traditional methodologies, while effective, often struggle to keep pace with the rapid advancements and the unique challenges presented by space environments. To bridge this gap, the APP4AD project (Advanced Payload Data Processing for Autonomy & Decision) introduces a novel approach designed to enhance the autonomy and decision-making processes of Earth Observation (EO) satellites and plan-

etary exploration rovers. This initiative is led by the Italian Space Agency (ASI) and developed by a consortium of Italian SMEs. The consortium includes Planetek Italia, Geophysical Applications Processing (GAP), and S.A.T.E. Systems & Advanced Technologies Engineering.

Figure 1: APP4AD Components

The primary objective of APP4AD is to transfer intelligence and analytical capabilities on-board space systems, thus enabling real-time data processing and autonomous decision-making. By incorporating advanced artificial intelligence (AI) techniques, the system aims to minimize reliance on Earth-based control stations, thereby reducing latency and improving response times to external events and unplanned situations. APP4AD can be classified in the Flight software data processing category that is typical of the on-board SWs of satellites and rovers. Such software elaborates payload data so the focus is mostly on image processing performance [1][2].

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Two primary scenarios illustrate the potential applications of APP4AD (Figure 1):

- **Earth Observation (EO) Scenario:** This scenario focuses on the detection of rapidly evolving and transient phenomena, such as oil spills, using Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data. The goal is to enable real-time, on-board processing to quickly identify and respond to such events, potentially preventing environmental disasters.
- **Planetary Exploration Scenario:** This scenario targets the autonomous exploration capabilities of rovers on planetary bodies like the Moon and Mars. It emphasizes the need to balance detailed observations with the efficient use of resources such as data transmission bandwidth and processing time.

2 Results

In this section, we present the preliminary results obtained from the implementation of the prototype SW for the two application cases.

2.1 EO Scenario Prototype

The DCNN model was trained on a large SAR image dataset including various types of oil spills, look alike, ships and novelties, using a combination of publicly available datasets such as CleanSeaNet [3] and TenGeoP-SARwv [4], and a custom dataset specifically created for this activity. This dataset is based

Figure 2: EO Scenario Algorithmic Workflow

on ERS-1/2, ENVISAT and Sentinel-1 SAR data and was created by integrating known case studies documented by scientific articles as well as oil spill cases identified by the authors in the Adriatic Sea in front of the port of Brindisi (Italy). Augmentation techniques were used to increase the size of the training dataset

and improve the performance of the DCNN model. The algorithm flow of the Earth Observation scenario is shown in Figure 2.

The performance of the proposed oil spill detection algorithm was checked first by analyzing the confusion matrix during the prediction phase. As shown in Figure 3, oil spill class was detected with an accuracy of 92.94%. Further tests were finally successfully

Figure 3: Normalized confusion matrix in the prediction phase of the proposed DCNN

carried out with a selection of 8 full-frame images acquired by the ERS-1/2 missions. As illustrated in the examples shown in Figure 4, the EO scenario prototype was able to detect correctly oil spill, look-alike, ship and novelty classes.

2.2 An end-to-end scenario demonstration for rover navigation toward novelty detection on Mars

The baseline dataset consists of two parts. The novelty detection dataset contains 99,132 multispectral images (64x64 with six channels), with 98,800 labeled as typical and 332 as novel, designed to train the model to detect novelties effectively due to its unbalanced nature[5]. For object detection and classification, the dataset comes from the Mars Science Laboratory Curiosity Rover, totaling 6,820 images (227x227). This is subdivided into 380 wide field images and 435 close-ups of Mars rocks, layers, and sand, derived by cropping from the original images.

The overall Algorithmic flow is shown in Figure 6. The first algorithm employed in the image analysis workflow is the Wide-Field Scene Recognition algorithm (WFSR-M), responsible for extracting features from an image. The classification of the image as either *navigation* or *scientific image* is determined based

Figure 4: Examples of detection in the EO scenario. Each row is a different case study. First column: SAR intensity image; second column: ground truth; third column: output of the DCNN segmentation and classification.

Figure 6: Rover Scenario Algorithmic Workflow

Figure 5: Example of Image processed by WFSR-M. On the first column there is the input image while on the second the extracted features

on the number of features the algorithm identifies. If a sufficient number of features are detected, the image is classified as *scientific image*, prompting further analysis. Otherwise, it is categorized as a *navigation image*, indicating a lack of elements of potential scientific interest. Figure 5 illustrates the application of WFSR-M on two different images. In the first row, only one feature is extracted, leading to the image’s classification as a navigation image. The second row, however, shows several features extracted at locations corresponding to terrain elements, which classify the image as of scientific interest. This effective differentiation between navigation and scientific images is quantified by the algorithm’s high accuracy rate of 93% in detecting wide field scientific images.

The features of the image classified as scientific image are passed as input to the Wide-Field Object Detection and Characterization algorithm (WFODC-M) that employs clustering algorithms to locate adjacent features within the image and creates bounding boxes around these areas. The regions within these bounding boxes are then cropped and classified (see Figure 7). A similar procedure is applied also to narrow-field images but, in this case, there is no classification. The final algorithm in the analysis process is the ‘novelty detection’ algorithm, which employs the

DASVDD[5] neural network. Its primary function is to determine the likelihood that the object being analyzed represents a novelty.

Figure 7: Example of wide-field image analyzed by WFODC-M

3 Discussion

The APP4AD project aims to enhance space system autonomy through advanced software architecture and edge component design. The modular and flexible architecture ensures compatibility across various hardware platforms. At its core, a High-Performance Computing Platform (HPCP) provides the necessary computational power for real-time data processing and AI operations ([6][7][8]). Additionally, an on-board Software Framework (FSW) supports essential applications and services for autonomous decision-making. APP4AD incorporates several key modules highlighted in Figure 8. The HW Abstrac-

Figure 8: APP4AD Product Tree

tion Layer ensures software compatibility across different hardware platforms. The Service Layer offers critical services like Monitoring and Control (M&C) using NASA’s core Flight System (cFS) and Application Support and AI functionalities via Planetek’s Spacekit framework. The Autonomy Extension Layer enhances the system’s autonomous capabilities through the Robot Operating System (ROS) framework ([9]), which aids in the development of robotic applications. One of APP4AD’s most innovative fea-

Figure 9: DCNN architecture proposed for the EO scenario

tures is its capability to perform AI-based data processing on-board using the Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX) format for efficient inference execution.

Figure 10: Logical process flow of APP4AD AI Training & Inference

This design improves real-time decision-making and resource management, crucial for modern space missions. In the context of Artificial Intelligence streams, one of the most innovative capabilities of APP4AD is the opportunity to enable the separation of the training and inference steps and allow only inference to be performed on-board. Figure 10 shows the logical process flow. The APP4AD software is designed for broad compatibility across different operating systems and hardware platforms. During the validation phase, the architecture was tested on a Microchip Polarfire Board (shown in Figure 11) running the specialized RISC-V OS[10][11]. Additionally, the software was developed and tested on common platforms like Linux and Windows. The tested application to support the optimized inference execution on the HW platform is VectorBlox Microchip SDK [12]. APP4AD's potential applications are illustrated through two primary scenarios: Earth Observation (EO) and Planetary Exploration.

Figure 11: Microchip Polarfire Board

In the Earth Observation scenario, APP4AD focuses on detecting oil spills in real-time using Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data. The system pre-processes SAR data, applies land-sea masks, and partitions images for analysis. A Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) (Figure 9) based on DeepLab v3+ with ResNet-18 ([13]) segments and classifies the images. The system achieved a 92.94% accuracy in detecting oil spills, with significant reductions in processing time, enabling near real-time detection.

In the Planetary Exploration scenario, APP4AD enhances autonomous navigation and scientific discovery by planetary rovers on the Moon and Mars (Figure 12). Techniques include Wide-Field Scene Recognition (WFSR-M) for analyzing wide-field images, Wide-Field Object Detection and Characterization (WFODC-M) for detecting and classifying ob-

Figure 12: Example of a validation environment for algorithms in the Rover Scenario

jects, and Narrow-Field Object Detection (NFOD-M) for detailed object analysis. Finally, there is a novelty detection part that has the task of establishing whether or not an image does or does not contain a novelty, i.e. an element that has not yet been seen([5][14]). The system demonstrated high accuracy and optimized processing times, ensuring real-time autonomous decision-making during rover missions. Simulations validated the rover's ability to navigate autonomously and investigate scientifically relevant scenes.

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